

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 6

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 6

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№6 (2024) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2024-6>

Бош муҳаррир:
Тўхтасинов Илҳом
п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:
Тухтасинов Илхом
д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:
Tuhtasinov Ilhom
DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли
ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким
ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил
ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммамед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода
ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар
ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
масбул котиб, PhD, доцент
(Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр
академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы
д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова
д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бокиева Гуландом
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким
д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил
д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммамед
к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт
Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддиқова Ирода
д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар
д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат
отв. секретарь, PhD, доцент
(Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov
academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed
Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort
University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda
Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar
Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Turobov Bekpulat
PhD Ass. prof. Senior Secretary
(Uzbekistan)

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Rashidova Manzura Bakhtiyorovna THE INFLUENCE OF CONFUCIAN TRADITIONS ON THE KOREAN LANGUAGE.....	5
2. Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich A SYSTEM OF EXERCISES AND TASKS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF WRITTEN SPEECH SKILLS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTICS.....	10
3. Ziyayeva Kamola Ziyaiddinovna THE LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL DIMENSIONS OF HUMOUR: A STUDY OF SPEECH GENRES AND THEIR ROLE IN COMMUNICATIN.....	15
4. Davlatova Xulkaroy Uktamovna, Botiova Valida Shuhrat qizi SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF SPEECH COMMUNICATION AND INTERNET COMMUNICATION.....	19
5. Jo‘raqulova Mushtariy O‘ZBEK TILI PARALLEL KORPUSINING LINGVISTIK TA‘MINOTI.....	24
6. Pardayeva Iroda Mamayunosovna ALISHER NAVOIY IJODIDA AMIR TEMUR VA TEMURIYLAR TASVIRI.....	29
7. Aliyeva Zebo Akram qizi MIRATIVLIK KATEGORIYASI GRAMMATIK KO‘RSATKICH SIFATIDA.....	35
8. Mirzayev Shukurullo Abduqodir o‘g‘li TOPIK II 53- YOZISH SAVOL TURLARI VA YOZISH USULLARI.....	41
9. Bayonkhanova Iroda Furkatovna KOREYS TILINI O‘RGANISHDA MAQOLLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIKLARI.....	47
10. Hasanov Suhrob Shavkat ugli SYMBOLS AND ALLEGORIES IN THE PROSE OF ISAJON SULTAN.....	53
11. Улаш Нематович Бобоев МОДЕЛЬ СТРАТЕГИЙ ПЕРЕВОДА НА РУССКИЙ ЯЗЫК ШОК-ТЕЙМЕНТА В СМИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ФРАНЦИИ.....	60
12. Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna AMPHIBOLOGY IN ENGLISH RELIGIOUS LEXICOLOGY.....	65
13. Eshimova Sharofat Kenjaboyevna SINESTEZIYA - METAFORANING BIR TURI SIFATIDA.....	70
14. Umirzoqova Oynisa THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE TEMPORAL CATEGORY IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES.....	76
15. Alibekova Dilrabo Abdiraimovna COHISION OF NATURALISM, OPTIMISM AND REALISIM IN THE WORKS OF HECTOR MALOT AND THEODOR DREISER.....	83
16. Gulirukhsor Ruzikulova Gofur kizi A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF FACE-RELATED IDIOMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK.....	88
17. Xalimova Firuza Rustamovna MATN DOIRASIDA BADIY KONSEPTNING SHAKLLANISHI.....	96
18. Xamidova Dilorom Olimjonovna LUQMON BO‘RIXONNING “JAZIRAMADAGI ODAMLAR” ROMANIDA BADIY TILNING IFODALANISHI.....	102

19. Xaydarova Nigora Tuxtasunovna AYOL VA ERKAKLARNING MULOQOT USULLARI.....	107
20. Shamshoda Rustamova O‘SMIR BOLALAR NUTQIDAGI INNOVATSIYALAR VA ULARNING IFODALANISHI.....	112
21. Karshieva Shokhista Kholikul kizi SYNTAX AND SEMANTICS OF ERGATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS.....	119
22. Musayeva Shaxlo Kudratovna QISSALARDA IKKINCHI JAHON URUSHI DAVRI VOQEALARI TASVIRINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI. (Nosir Fozilov asarlari misolida).....	125
23. N.J.Sulaymanova IJOBIY BAHO PRAGMATIK MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI NUTQIY AKTLAR.....	131
24. Azimbayeva Nargiza Tuxtamuradovna O‘ZBEK VA FORS TILLARIDA XULQ-ATVORNI IFODALOVCHI LEKSIK KONSTRUKSIYALAR TASNIFI.....	135
25. Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmuradovna THE ROLE OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGY IN CROSS-CULTURAL COMMUNICATION.....	139
26. Gulruxsor Xoliyorova TERMINOLOGIK TEZAVRUSLARNING LINGVISTIK XOSLANISHI.....	143
27. Alisher Rustamov Abduhakimovich THE HISTORY OF TEACHING AND LEARNING ENGLISH WRITING SKILLS IN UZBEKISTAN (POST-SOVIET STATE). PEDAGOGICAL DIAGNOSTIC APPROACH.....	149
28. Kubaeva Nafisa Alisher qizi UNLOCKING THE POWER OF IDIOMS: HOW FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE ENRICHES COMMUNICATION.....	154
29. Dilafro‘z Amonova KOREYS ADABIYOTI TARIXIDA AYOLLAR IJODIYOTI.....	158
30. Obruyeva Gulchexra Xamrokulovna ATOQLI OTLARNING FRAZEOLOGIK BIRLIKLAR TARKIBIDA APELLATIVIZATSIYAGA UCHRASHI...	164
31. Esanova Maftuna Bahodirovna YUNON-LOTIN TIBBIYOT ATAMALARINING TARIXI VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY TIBBIYOTDAGI O‘RNI.....	168
32. Azimova Yulduz Baxtiyor qizi AVTOBIOGRAFIK DISKURSNING UMUMIY TAVSIFI.....	173
33. Maxmudova Dilshoda Kurbonbayevna KOMPOZITSION TASHKILLANISH VA PEYZAJ MODIFIKATSIYASI.....	177

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Karshieva Shokhista Kholikul kiziIndependent researcher of
Samarkand state institute of foreign languages
email: shohistaqarshiyeva07@gmail.com**SYNTAX AND SEMANTICS OF ERGATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15069197>**ABSTRACT**

This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the syntactic and semantic properties of ergative constructions, emphasizing their unique role in English grammar. By delving into key linguistic theories and scholarly discussions, it explores how ergative verbs function in sentence structures, transitioning seamlessly between transitive and intransitive forms. The study highlights the dual behavior of ergative verbs, which can encode both causative actions and the affectedness of entities within a single linguistic framework. Through this duality, ergative constructions challenge traditional subject-object alignments, offering insights into agent-patient dynamics, causation, and syntactic flexibility.

Furthermore, the research underscores the significance of ergative constructions in broadening our understanding of how language encodes meaning, agency, and event structure. The findings not only clarify the patterns of ergativity in English but also contribute to the broader discussion on cross-linguistic syntactic and semantic principles, revealing parallels with other languages. This exploration of ergative constructions enriches the study of grammar and has potential applications in both linguistic theory and language teaching, particularly in addressing the complexities faced by non-native speakers.

Key words: Ergative construction, English syntax, causation, agent-patient roles, transitivity, intransitivity, unaccusative verbs, syntactic flexibility.

Qarshiyeva Shoxista Xoliqul qiziSamarqand davlat chet tillari instituti
mustaqil izlanuvchisi
email: shohistaqarshiyeva07@gmail.com**ERGATIV KONSTRUKSIYALAR SINTAKSISI VA SEMANTIKASI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqola ergativ tuzilmalarni sintaktik va semantik jihatdan kompleks tahlil qilishni taklif etadi hamda ularning ingliz tili grammatikasidagi o'ziga xos o'rnini yoritadi. Asosiy tilshunoslik nazariyalari va ilmiy muhokamalarga chuqur kirib boorish orqali, maqola ergativ fe'llarning jumla tuzilmasidagi vazifalarini, o'timli va o'timsiz shakllar orasida hech bir qiyinchiliksiz o'tish xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. Tadqiqot ergativ fe'llarning ikki tomonlama xatti-

harakatlarini, ya'ni sababli harakatlarni ham, obyektarning ta'sirlanishini ham bir til tizimi doirasida ifodalash qobiliyatini ta'kidlaydi. Bu dualizm orqali ergativ tuzilmalar an'anaviy subyekt-obyekt o'zaro bog'liqliklarini shubha ostiga qo'yib, agent-patsiyent (ega-to'ldiruvchi) rollari, sabablilik va sintaktik moslashuvchanlik haqida yangi bilimlar taqdim etadi.

Bundan tashqari, tadqiqot ergativ tuzilmalarni tilning ma'no, agentlik va hodisa tuzilmasini qanday ifodalashini kengroq tushunishda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Ushbu natijalar nafaqat ingliz tilidagi ergativlik andozalarini aniqlashtiradi, balki tilshunoslikning kross-lingvistik sintaktik va semantik prinsiplari bo'yicha davom etayotgan munozaralarga ham hissa qo'shadi.

Ergativ konstruksiyalarni bunday o'rganish grammatika tadqiqotlarini boyitadi va lingvistik nazariya hamda til o'rgatishda, xususan, chet tili o'rganuvchilar duch keladigan murakkabliklarni bartaraf etishda amaliy qo'llanmalarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: ergativ tuzilmalar, ingliz sintaksisi, sabablilik, agent-pasient rollari, tranzitivlik, intranzitivlik, unakkuzativ fe'llar, sintaktik moslashuvchanlik.

Шохиста Каршиева Холикул кизи

Независимый исследователь в
Самаркандский государственный
институт иностранных языков
email: shohistaqarshiyeva07@gmail.com

СИНТАКСИС И СЕМАНТИКА ЭРГАТИВНЫХ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлен всесторонний анализ синтаксических и семантических свойств эргативных конструкций с акцентом на их уникальную роль в грамматике английского языка. Исследуя ключевые лингвистические теории и научные дискуссии, авторы рассматривают, как эргативные глаголы функционируют в структуре предложений, свободно переходя между переходными и непереходными формами. Исследование подчеркивает двойственную природу эргативных глаголов, которые могут одновременно выражать причинно-следственные действия и затронутость объектов в рамках одной языковой системы.

Благодаря этой двойственности эргативные конструкции ставят под сомнение традиционное соответствие субъектно-объектных отношений, предоставляя ценные знания о динамике агент-пациент, причинности и синтаксической гибкости. Кроме того, исследование подчеркивает важность эргативных конструкций для более глубокого понимания того, как язык кодирует значения, агентность и структуру событий. Результаты не только уточняют особенности эргативности в английском языке, но и вносят вклад в более широкую дискуссию о кросс-лингвистических синтаксических и семантических принципах, выявляя параллели с другими языками.

Изучение эргативных конструкций обогащает исследование грамматики и имеет потенциальное применение как в лингвистической теории, так и в преподавании языка, особенно в решении сложностей, с которыми сталкиваются изучающие язык как иностранный.

Ключевые слова: эргативные конструкции, синтаксис английского языка, причинность, роли агента и пациента, переходность, непереходность, унаккузативные глаголы, синтаксическая гибкость.

INTRODUCTION

Ergativity is a linguistic concept that has intrigued researchers for its role in distinguishing language and structuring sentence constructions. Unlike the nominative-accusative alignment found in many languages, ergative constructions appear in verbs that allow for both transitive and intransitive usage, where the intransitive form involves an affected subject rather than an acting agent.

For instance, in “The glass broke”, “the glass” itself undergoes the breaking without an explicit agent, whereas in “She broke the glass”, an agent (she) is introduced to cause the action.

The study of ergative constructions in English offers significant insights into how syntax and semantics interact to convey meaning. Although ergative structures are not dominant in English, they provide a fascinating deviation from typical nominative-accusative patterns and suggest potential cross-linguistic similarities with languages that use ergativity as their main alignment system. Linguists have debated the implications of ergativity for understanding agent-patient relationships, causation, and the broader argument structure of verbs. For example, Dixon [Dixon 1994: 3] argues that ergative structures highlight a universal tendency in human language to adapt syntax according to the nature of the event described, especially in languages with a strong focus on event structure and causation. This study aims to deepen the understanding of how ergative constructions function in English, both syntactically and semantically. By examining ergative verbs’ ability to transition between transitive and intransitive forms, the paper explores how these structures reshape traditional grammatical categories. Specifically, this article will:

1. Analyze the syntactic properties of ergative constructions, focusing on how verb argument structures adapt.
2. Explore the semantic implications of ergative verbs, particularly their role in encoding causation and agency.

The article synthesizes the perspectives of prominent linguists to outline the unique attributes of ergative constructions and contributes to the ongoing conversation regarding the universality and linguistic function of ergative structures.

METHODS

This study employs a qualitative approach, relying on a comprehensive literature review of key studies addressing ergativity in syntax and semantics. Given the theoretical nature of ergative analysis, the research draws upon linguistic theories, grammatical analyses, and syntactic data examples from scholarly sources. By synthesizing previous findings, the study provides a structured examination of ergative constructions within the English language.

Data collection

Relevant linguistic studies were selected from both historical and contemporary research on ergativity. Primary sources include research articles, books, and linguistic analyses focused on syntax and semantics, particularly works that address ergative structures in English and other languages. Authors such as Dixon (1994), Comrie (1978), and Levin and Rappaport Hovav (1995) were chosen for their foundational contributions to understanding ergative syntax and semantics. These sources were supplemented by more recent studies to incorporate current perspectives on causation and verb argument structure.

Analytical framework

The study employs a thematic analysis to categorize and interpret findings on ergative constructions. The analysis focuses on:

1. Syntactic structure: An examination of ergative verbs within sentence structures, emphasizing transitions between transitive and intransitive forms.
2. Semantic interpretation: Analysis of the semantic nuances conveyed by ergative verbs, particularly in terms of causation, agent roles, and patient roles. This component draws from established linguistic frameworks to clarify how ergative structures affect meaning.

The methodological approach allows for a structured synthesis of diverse linguistic perspectives, helping to contextualize the role of ergative constructions within English and in relation to broader syntactic and semantic principles.

RESULTS

Syntactic structures of ergative constructions

Ergative constructions in English present unique syntactic properties that challenge the traditional nominative-accusative alignment. Ergative verbs such as *break*, *open*, and *sink* operate in both transitive and intransitive forms, with their syntactic roles shifting based on usage. In transitive sentences (e.g., *She broke the glass*), the subject is the agent causing the action, while the object (the

glass) is affected by it. However, in intransitive constructions (e.g., The glass broke), the same noun phrase – the glass becomes the subject and inherently undergoes the action, thus embodying the patient role.

This dual behavior reveals an essential syntactic feature of ergative verbs: their ability to align arguments differently based on causative or non-causative contexts [Dixon 1994: 3]. The syntactic flexibility allows English speakers to alternate between agent-focused and patient focused constructions without altering the verb's core meaning, underscoring the capacity of ergative verbs to defy traditional subject-object roles.

Another significant syntactic aspect is the pattern of “unaccusativity” observed in many ergative verbs. According to Perlmutter, unaccusative verbs feature subjects that would typically be objects in corresponding transitive sentences, making them syntactically analogous to ergative verbs. In the sentence “The cake baked”, the subject the cake is not an agent but rather the entity affected by the action. This aligns with unaccusative syntactic patterns where the grammatical subject behaves as a semantic patient, further illustrating the complex syntactic structure of ergative verbs in English.

Semantic implications of ergative constructions

From a semantic perspective, ergative constructions contribute significantly to expressing causation, agency, and the affected state of entities. When ergative verbs appear intransitively, the absence of an explicit agent often implies an inherent causative force within the action itself. For instance, in the sentence “The door opened”, the semantic focus is on the change of state of the door rather than on who caused the action [Levin and Rappaport Hovav 1995: 6]. The implicit causation differentiates ergative verbs from purely intransitive verbs, which do not imply an external cause.

Moreover, ergative constructions highlight the affectedness of the subject, as seen in verb like sink, melt, and freeze, where the semantic emphasis lies on the transformation or effect experienced by the subject. As Anderson argues, ergative verbs allow languages to foreground the affectedness of entities, making the change of state a central semantic feature [Anderson 2005: 1]. This affectedness is particularly noticeable when inanimate subjects undergo an action without a human or animate agent, as in “The ice melted”. Such constructions present the subject as inherently susceptible to the action, reinforcing the verb's patient-like role in conveying the result of an action rather than its initiation.

DISCUSSION

Findings illustrate that ergative constructions in English occupy a unique syntactic and semantic space within the language, blending elements of both transitivity and intransitivity. This dual nature enables ergative verbs to adapt to diverse syntactic roles, allowing for a more nuanced expression of agency and affectedness. Syntactically, ergative constructions offer flexibility by allowing the subject to shift from an agentive role in transitive sentences to a patient role in intransitive ones. This shift aligns English with ergative languages in certain respects, demonstrating that ergative patterns are not exclusive to languages with ergative-absolutive alignment, but can exist alongside nominative-accusative systems.

Cross-linguistically, English ergative verbs exhibit parallels with ergative constructions in other languages, supporting the view that ergativity may reflect universal linguistic principles. For instance, languages such as Basque and Hindi exhibit ergative alignment in their verb structures, often prioritizing affected entities over agents. Although English lacks full ergative-absolutive alignment, its use of ergative verbs indicates that the language possesses latent ergative characteristics. This finding supports Dixon's theory that ergative constructions reflect an underlying tendency in human language to reframe argument structures based on the nature of events being described [Dixon 1994: 3].

The semantic analysis underscores the significance of ergative constructions in encoding causation implicitly, allowing speakers to communicate causative events without explicitly mentioning an agent. This feature is particularly useful in contexts where the agent is unknown, unimportant, or assumed by the listener. The implicit causation within ergative constructions enhances the expressiveness of language, giving speakers tools to shift focus between the cause and effect of an action. Levin and Rappaport Hovav argue that this implicit causation is integral to the

semantics of ergative verbs, as it reinforces their role in denoting changes of state and affectedness [Levin and Rappaport Hovav 1995: 6].

The implications of ergative constructions extend to practical applications, especially in the teaching of English grammar. For non-native speakers, mastering ergative verbs can be challenging due to their dual roles in transitive and intransitive contexts. Jones suggests that understanding ergativity can improve comprehension and fluency by helping learners grasp the nuanced ways English encodes agency and affectedness [Jones 2010: 5]. Introducing ergative constructions into language instruction may enable students to appreciate the versatility of English verbs, ultimately enhancing their grasp of sentence structure and meaning.

Additionally, this study opens avenues for further research into the cognitive processing of ergative constructions. Psycholinguistic studies could explore whether ergative structures, with their typical subject-object alignment, impact sentence comprehension differently compared to typical nominative-accusative patterns. Investigating how speakers mentally process ergative constructions may reveal new insights into the cognitive mechanisms underlying syntactic flexibility and semantic interpretation.

Overall, ergative constructions in English offer a compelling lens through which to explore the intersection of syntax and semantics. By challenging traditional grammatical roles, ergative verbs broaden the expressive possibilities of language, highlighting the diverse ways in which human languages can encode meaning and agency.

CONCLUSION

This study provides an in-depth exploration of ergative constructions in English, focusing on their unique syntactic and semantic properties. Ergative constructions challenge traditional grammatical roles by allowing verbs to shift between transitive and intransitive forms, where the subject can alternate between agent and patient roles. This syntactic flexibility offers speakers the option to emphasize either the initiator of an action or the affected entity demonstrating that English – typically classified as nominative-accusative – contains structures that align with ergative-absolutive patterns seen in other languages. The results underscore that ergative verbs, through their unaccusative properties, introduce a level of complexity and expressiveness to English sentence construction.

On a semantic level, ergative constructions enable implicit causation, where an action's effect is conveyed without explicitly stating the agent. This implicit causative meaning highlights the affectedness of the subject, making ergative constructions particularly useful in contexts where the focus is on the outcome or change of state rather than on the actor. By revealing patterns of causation, agency, and affectedness, ergative verbs play a significant role in enriching English's expressive range and providing insights into universal tendencies in human language.

The implications of these findings are broad, suggesting that ergative structures may serve as a bridge between languages with different alignment systems and offering practical insights for teaching and language acquisition. For linguists, understanding ergativity deepens our knowledge of argument structure, syntactic variation, and the cognitive processes involved in language comprehension. Further research into ergative constructions, especially from cross-linguistic and psycholinguistic perspectives, will continue to enhance our understanding of how language systems encode and interpret complex relationships between actions and entities.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, S. R. (2005). Ergativity and language universals. *Language typology and syntactic description* (pp. 83-105). Cambridge University Press.
2. Qarshiyeva Sh.X. (2024). Navigating the complexity of ergative verbs in the English language. *NamDU ilmiy axborotnomasi*, 2024/11, pp. 567-570. <https://journal.namdu.uz/file/2024121113095912.pdf>
3. Dixon, R. M. W. (1994). *Ergativity*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 1-46, 74-105.

4. Qarshiyeva Sh.X. (2024). The dynamic verbs in English and their ergative features. *Ilm sarchashmalari*, 2024-12/2, pp. 180-183. <https://ilmsarchashmalari.uz/year/2024>
5. Jones, C. (2010). Grammar Teaching and the Ergative Construction. *English Language Teaching Journal*, 64(3), 322-331.
6. Levin, B., & Rappaport Hovav, M. (1995). *Unaccusativity: At the syntax-lexical semantics interface*. MIT Press, pp. 1-36, 92-130
7. Qarshiyeva Sh.X. (2024). Tilshunoslikda tadqiqot obyekti sifatida ingliz tili ergativ fe'llarining o'rganilish tarixi, 2024/6, pp. 392-395. <https://journal.namdu.uz/file/2024092316462209.pdf>
8. Karshieva, S. K. kizi. (2024). The Concept of pragmatics in linguistics. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 2(2), 544–548. Retrieved from <https://grnjournal.us/index.php/STEM/article/view/3427>
9. Shokhista, K. (2024). National-Cultural Specificity of Phraseological Units. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 3(3), 177–180. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/2354>
10. Qarshiyeva , S. K. (2024). Ingliz tilida ergativ fe'llarning o'rganish masalalari. *Молодые ученые*, 2(5), 30–32. извлечено от <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/27494>

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

7 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 7, НОМЕР 6

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 7, ISSUE 6

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000